

THE METHODS AND WAYS OF BEING GOOD TEACHER

Turayeva Ugiloy

sophomore of SamSIFL

Scientific tutors: **Zubaydova Nigina**

Iskandarova Liliya

torayevaogiloy1309@gmail.com

Phone number: +998883041309

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Annotation: In the article, you can learn ways of how to be good teacher and getting several qualities to reach it, what good teachers start their profession with, how to keep your teaching skills fresh with professional quality and important hard skills for teachers to develop.

Key words: top qualities, adaptability, collaboration, creativity, empathy, engagement, patience, respect, professional development, soft hard skills, free of bias, inherent imbalance of power and collaborative skills.

Every educator wants to get career with high quality. Therefore, they research a lot to improve their own experience. Some of them are in wrong way and they are disturbed by the side of unnecessary methods and the methods do not help them to improve their skills. Doing research truly helps us to get top qualities in every field easily. Some teachers probably stand out as an exceptional source of encouragement and inspiration. Maybe, it is teacher of your kindergarten, school, college. This is because, they possessed many of professional methods, characteristics.

Firstly, effective teachers share certain universal traits in common. For example, all great educators have the ability to listen actively – not only to their students, but also to their colleagues, school administrators, and students' family members. This is basic efficient way to be great educator. Furthermore, we had better have an adaptability, collaboration, creativity, empathy, engagement, patience as well as respect to be the best one of teachers. To get an adaptability, we should not become immobilized by stress or indecision. We need to continuously evaluate what's working for our students – and even more importantly, what is not working. Being adaptable and flexible allows you to flow between different theories of learning and modes of teaching something we will discuss momentarily. This is a must for teachers. To get an empathy is the ability to understand what another person is feeling or experiencing – put simply, putting yourself in another person's shoes. As a teacher, it is vital to practice empathy instead of making assumptions – for instance, making efforts to understand and address the root issue that's causing a student to fall behind their peers, perform more poorly than they used to, or lash out in class. Patience is also useful way. It is important both to possess and to model for your students – who, as we discussed in our post on theories of learning, may view you as a role model and emulate your behavior. Having a reserve of patience will make it easier for you to work through each student's unique struggles and challenges, which may be difficult or slow-going to overcome.

Engagement is also need for teachers. They should use interesting materials, methods and ways to engage students in case students get bored in lesson. If you want to effectively diagnose and help overcome students' unique obstacles and challenges, active listening is vital. Seek feedback, encourage honesty, provide ways for students to contact you easily, and be attentive

whenever you listen, always trying to read between the lines and assess body language while you are communicating. Learn more about how and why you should improve your active listening skills. To be the best educator you should be free of bias. As an educator, you will be responsible for teaching an extraordinarily wide range of students. To combat inequality and discrimination and insuring fairness, you need to assess your students' needs in a way that is free from bias. Between student and teacher, there should be inherent imbalance of power.

Another key trait I explored on this list. Whatever you teach first graders or doctoral students, you will need the ability to innovate, think outside the box, and find novel solutions to challenges, which will empower you to meet a wider range of students' needs. Being creative as an educator will also help you to foster creativity in your students – an essential skill they will need for countless career paths. You also need strong collaborative skills to ensure you can work well with others consistently. If your goal is to become an educator or transition into an educational leadership position. To be prepared for a wide range of scenarios and challenges in the classroom, you should be flexible and adaptable, it is important for good preparation.

In 2006, psychologist Carol Dweck introduced the concept of “growth mindsets” vs. “fixed mindsets” in her book *Mindset: The Psychology of Success*. According to Dweck individuals with a fixed mindset perceive assets like intelligence as being determined early in life, which can cause obstacles or challenges to seem insurmountable or overwhelming. In contrast to a fixed mindset, individuals who have a growth mindset believe that traits like intelligence and creativity can be developed with practice. Another area where traits like adaptability, empathy, and patience come into play for educators is having the ability to accommodate students who learn at different paces, using different styles and methods, within the same classroom or group. As an educator, you meet a new group of students every year – and every year, there are new developments around the science and psychology of learning. In short, students' needs change over time, like the way that social media and mobile devices have become key learning tools among Gen Z students compared to previous generations.

To get high quality of teaching, you should follow the advices in detail as well as you had better pay attention to the advice carefully if you want to be the best one. The determinants are adaptability, empathy, patience, engagement, active listening, free of bias, inherent imbalance of power and collaborative skills.

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